

Review

The Role of Acupuncture and Herbal Medicine in Infertility Management: A Narrative Review of Current Evidence.

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Abstract

Background: Infertility is a global public health concern affecting 9–18% of couples worldwide. Conventional treatments, including assisted reproductive technologies (ART), are often associated with limited success rates, adverse effects, and significant emotional and financial burden. Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), particularly acupuncture and herbal medicine, has been increasingly explored as a complementary approach to infertility management.

Methods: A narrative review was conducted using PubMed to identify randomised controlled trials (RCTs) published between 2019 and 2025. Eligible studies evaluated acupuncture and/or herbal medicine in infertile populations. Only peer-reviewed articles in English, Spanish, French, or Portuguese were included. Data extraction focused on intervention protocols, reproductive outcomes (e.g., pregnancy and live birth rates, endometrial and ovarian parameters, sperm quality), and proposed mechanisms of action.

Results: Thirteen RCTs were included, comprising eight studies on acupuncture and five on herbal medicine. In women, acupuncture, particularly transcutaneous electrical acupoint stimulation (TEAS), was associated with improved implantation, clinical pregnancy, and live birth rates in recurrent implantation failure and with enhanced ovarian response and endometrial receptivity in PCOS and poor ovarian response. Herbal medicine, including *Dingkun Pill (DKP)*, *Zishen Yutai Pill (ZYP)*, and *Qixiong Zhongzi Decoction (QZD)*, demonstrated potential benefits in endometrial thickness, luteal function, tubal patency, and sperm motility, though findings were mixed, with some trials reporting no significant differences. Mechanistically, both acupuncture and herbal medicine appear to act through neuroendocrine regulation, improved uterine and ovarian blood flow, antioxidant effects, and modulation of immune and stress responses.

Conclusions: Acupuncture and herbal medicine appear safe and potentially beneficial as complementary therapies for infertility, improving reproductive parameters and supporting emotional well-being. However, the evidence remains limited by small sample sizes and methodological heterogeneity. Further high-quality, multicentre RCTs with standardised protocols and long-term follow-up are needed to establish their role in clinical practice.

Keywords: Fertility; Infertility; Acupuncture; Herbal Medicine; Traditional Chinese Medicine.

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1. Introduction

Infertility (IF) is recognised by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a global public health problem, affecting approximately 9% to 18% of couples worldwide¹⁻³. It is defined as the inability to conceive after one or more years of regular, unprotected sexual intercourse, a condition that may affect both men and women⁴⁻⁶.

In women, infertility can be caused by a variety of complex factors, such as menstrual irregularities, endometriosis, pelvic adhesions, ovulatory dysfunction, tubal obstructions,

and uterine abnormalities ^{2,6,7}. Specific conditions such as congenital gonadal dysgenesis, hyperprolactinemia, diminished ovarian reserve (DOR), polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), luteinized unruptured follicle syndrome (LUFs), and chronic anovulation also contribute to infertility ⁸. Psychological aspects—such as stress, depression, fatigue, and sexual dissatisfaction—may also play a role ².

Male infertility is a complex and multifactorial condition, influenced by a wide range of factors, including biological (genetic alterations, urogenital tract infections, varicocele), behavioural (smoking, excessive alcohol consumption, inadequate body mass index, risky sexual behaviour, use of psychoactive substances), environmental (industrial chemicals, pesticides), and sociodemographic (advancing age) factors ^{9,10}.

Most commonly used therapeutic methods for infertility include medical treatments and complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) ¹¹. Treatments may involve fertility drugs, surgery, in vitro fertilisation (IVF), or other ART ¹²⁻¹⁵. Commonly used drugs in clinical practice include clomiphene citrate (CC), human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), human menopausal gonadotropin (hMG), gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), GnRH analogues, bromocriptine, and cabergoline ¹⁶⁻²².

However, these drugs are associated with numerous physical and psychological adverse reactions, such as breast tenderness, swelling, rashes, mood changes, depression, nausea, vomiting, headaches, loss of bone density, among others ^{5,23}. Available treatments face relevant limitations, including relatively low live birth rates, need for multiple therapeutic cycles, risk of adverse effects, and high financial and emotional costs for both patients and society ²⁴⁻²⁸.

Given this scenario, it is necessary and urgent to explore complementary alternative approaches that may enhance the outcomes of conventional treatments. In this context, TCM emerges as a promising option, based on the principle that health results from the harmonious balance of internal biological functions ⁷.

Among TCM techniques, acupuncture stands out, consisting of inserting fine needles at specific points of the body. In some approaches, this practice may be combined with electrical stimulation of the needles, producing effects on the nervous, endocrine, circulatory, and other systems ²⁹.

Herbal medicine is another TCM therapy that uses medicinal plants selected according to study objectives, properties, and therapeutic benefits. These may help prevent oxidative stress, modulate germ cell proliferation and apoptosis, improve semen quality, as well as regulate hormonal balance and immune function ⁶.

Beyond infertility, TCM has demonstrated positive outcomes in treating other clinical conditions, such as cancer ³⁰, modulation of immune markers, prevention of autoimmune disease progression, such as Hashimoto's disease ³¹, gastrointestinal disorders ^{32,33}, dermatology ³⁴, and mental health conditions ³⁵.

Regarding infertility, rigorous investigations are needed to ensure the reliability, quality, and accuracy of results. Many studies focus on specific conditions and fertility markers, yet fail to conclusively demonstrate the efficacy of TCM in terms of pregnancy and birth rates, often presenting limitations related to study duration and follow-up. Furthermore, it is essential to understand how different TCM practices—used individually or in combination—may contribute to better clinical outcomes.

This review aims to map, analyse, and synthesise available evidence on the use of acupuncture, moxibustion, and herbal medicine in infertility treatment. It also seeks to identify knowledge gaps, guide future research, and evaluate more effective strategies for managing infertility. The guiding research question is: What are the effects and mechanisms of acupuncture and herbal medicine in infertility?

2. Methodology

2.1. Research Question

The primary research question guiding this review was based on the following PICO framework:

- P (Population): Individuals diagnosed with infertility (both male and female, of various aetiologies).
- I (Intervention/Exposure): Acupuncture and/or herbal medicine (TCM).
- C (Comparison): Placebo, sham intervention, no intervention, conventional medical treatment for infertility, or other complementary therapies.
- O (Outcome): Clinical pregnancy rates, live birth rates, ovulation rates, sperm parameters (for male infertility), hormone levels (e.g., FSH, LH, E2), changes in underlying conditions contributing to infertility (e.g., PCOS, endometriosis), adverse events, and reported mechanisms of action (e.g., changes in blood flow, neuroendocrine regulation, anti-inflammatory effects).

2.2. Search strategy

A comprehensive search was performed on PubMed to identify relevant studies. The database was searched from 2019 to 2025, and the following combinations of search terms are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Combinations of search terms used in PubMed.

Search terms
Female
Infertility, Female [MeSH Terms] acupuncture therapy [MeSH Terms]
Infertility, Female [MeSH Terms] phytotherapy [MeSH Terms]
Infertility, Female [MeSH Terms] drugs, chinese herbal [MeSH Terms]
Infertility, Female [MeSH Terms] traditional chinese medicine [MeSH Terms]
Infertility, Female [MeSH Terms] acupoint [MeSH Terms]
Male
Infertility, Male [MeSH Terms] acupuncture therapy [MeSH Terms]
Infertility, Male [MeSH Terms] phytotherapy [MeSH Terms]
Infertility, Male [MeSH Terms] drugs, chinese herbal [MeSH Terms]
Infertility, Male [MeSH Terms] traditional chinese medicine [MeSH Terms]
Infertility, Male [MeSH Terms] acupoint [MeSH Terms]
Other
Infertility [MeSH Terms] acupuncture therapy [MeSH Terms]
Infertility [MeSH Terms] drugs, chinese herbal [MeSH Terms]
Infertility [MeSH Terms] traditional chinese medicine [MeSH Terms]

2.3. Eligibility Criteria

Studies were included if they met the following criteria: (1) Studies should have assessed the use Acupuncture and/or Chinese Herbal medicine as an intervention; (2) Studies should have investigated their application in infertile populations; (3) Studies should have been published in scientific peer-reviewed journals; (4) Studies should have been published in English, Spanish, French or Portuguese; (5) Studies' methodology should be RCTs.

Studies would have been excluded if they were in Mandarin (abstract and or full text). The researchers were not able to guarantee official validations of articles written in Mandarin.

2.4. Study Selection

Two researchers (H.M.S. and T.M.F.) screened titles and abstracts against the predefined eligibility criteria. Any disagreements were resolved through discussion or by arbitration with two researchers (C.S.S. and I.C.L.).

The full texts of potentially eligible studies were then retrieved and independently assessed by the authors.

2.5. Data Extraction

All the authors of this research participated in data extraction (2019-2025 scientific articles). Upon randomly distributing the retrieved articles, the author would extract data to an Excel (Microsoft - Redmond, Washington, United States) sheet. A second author reviewed the extraction data. If the reviewer had any disagreement with the initial extraction, a third reviewer would intervene.

2.6. Ethical Considerations

As this review synthesises publicly available data, ethical approval was not required.

3. Results

According to the database search, a total of 82 research items were found, of which 46 were excluded after duplicate removal. Abstract screening led to the exclusion of 17 articles. Of the remaining 19 research items, 6 were removed after full-text screening, 13 remained and were included in our final analysis. Each stage is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flow diagram of the selection process.

Of the included studies, 5 focused on the assessment of phytotherapy as a treatment method, 8 on the assessment of Acupuncture. Moreover, 12 studies focused on female infertility and 2 on male infertility. Table 2 summarises the included studies.

Table 2. Included studies and respective objectives, samples and protocols, and main results.

Reference	Objective	Sample and protocol	Main results
Acupuncture – Male (1 study)			
Yu <i>et al.</i> ³⁶	Evaluate the effect of TEAS on sperm parameters and underlying molecular mechanisms.	121 patients with oligozoospermia, asthenozoospermia, or oligoasthenozoospermia were randomised into four groups: TEAS 2 Hz (n=31), TEAS 100 Hz (n=31), sham stimulation (n=29), and control (n=30, lifestyle advice only). Treatment at BL23, ST36, CV1, CV4 for 2 months	2 Hz TEAS significantly improved sperm count and motility compared to the sham and control groups. Significant increases in seminal zinc, NAG, and fructose, as well as increased CIB1 and reduced CDK1 expression, were observed. Suggests TEAS at 2 Hz may improve sperm motility and function in men with abnormal semen parameters.
Acupuncture – Female (7 studies)			
Shuai <i>et al.</i> ³⁷	Evaluate TEAS in women with recurrent implantation failure (RIF) undergoing IVF.	122 women were randomised into TEAS vs. sham TEAS. 30 min, 2 Hz stimulation on SP6, CV3, CV4, Zigong every 2 days from ovarian stimulation until embryo transfer.	Implantation, clinical pregnancy, and live birth rates were significantly higher in the TEAS group (24.3%, 32.8%, 27.9%) vs. sham (12.1%, 16.4%, 13.1%). TEAS significantly improved IVF outcomes in women with RIF.
Xie <i>et al.</i> ³⁸	Assess TCM acupoint patches with hot compresses for pain relief during HyCoSy.	150 women randomized: control (psychological support + music), hot compress, combined treatment (TCM patch + hot compress).	Significant reductions in NRS pain scores in the combined group. Higher comfort scores and reduced grade 3 pain compared to other groups. Safe and effective to improve patient comfort during HyCoSy.
Guven <i>et al.</i> ³⁹	Investigate the effect of acupuncture before and after embryo transfer (ET) among women undergoing IVF.	72 women randomised: acupuncture group (n=36) with 3 sessions (1 week before, 30 min before, and 30 min after ET) vs. control (n=36, no acupuncture).	Higher β -HCG, clinical pregnancy, ongoing pregnancy, and live birth rates in the acupuncture group. Anxiety scores significantly reduced.
Yuan <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁰	Investigate acupuncture in patients with poor ovarian response (POR) receiving controlled ovarian stimulation (COS).	67 women with POR were randomised to COS + acupuncture vs. COS only.	Higher rates of high-quality embryos and available embryos in the acupuncture group. Suggests acupuncture as a safe and effective adjuvant to ovarian stimulation
Altutunji <i>et al.</i> ⁴¹	Assess acupuncture during the follicular phase on AMH levels and ART outcomes in PCOS patients undergoing IVF.	102 infertile PCOS patients randomised: acupuncture (n=33) vs. control (n=69).	Higher numbers of transferred embryos, clinical pregnancies, and ongoing pregnancies in the acupuncture group. Lower OHSS risk.
Wu <i>et al.</i> ⁴²	Observe acupuncture effects on endometrium and pregnancy outcomes in PCOS patients undergoing IVF-ET.	83 patients were randomised to acupuncture (n=40) vs. control (n=43). A routine long GnRH agonist protocol was used in both groups. Acupuncture is administered every other day, alternating 2 point groups.	Acupuncture improved endometrial quality, regulated serum E2 and P, and increased clinical pregnancy rate. No serious adverse events.

Zhai <i>et al.</i> ⁴³	Evaluate TEAS modes on ovarian responses and pregnancy outcomes in IVF-ET patients.	200 infertile patients were randomised into four TEAS groups (20–50 mA) and one sham group (5 mA). Treated daily for 10–13 days at CV4, CV3, SP6, EX-CA1, KI13.	Higher clinical pregnancy, embryo implantation, and live birth rates in TEAS groups vs. control. Improvements in vascular function and a reduction in kidney deficiency/blood stasis symptoms. Fewer adverse events.
Herbal medicine – Female (4 studies)			
Jin <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁴	Assess DKP with hormone therapy in women with thin endometrium infertility.	307 patients randomized: experimental (estradiol + dydrogesterone + DKP) vs. control (hormonal only).	DKP significantly improved endometrial thickness, luteal function, and cumulative pregnancy rate (29.2% vs. 15.7%).
Song <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁵	Evaluate DKP supplementation in women with expected POR (POSEIDON group 4).	462 patients were randomised to DKP vs. placebo.	No significant difference in ongoing pregnancy overall. Subgroup (age 35–37) showed higher ongoing pregnancy with DKP (41.8% vs. 25.4%).
Chen <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁶	Evaluate ZYP in FET cycles.	880 women were randomised to ZYP vs. placebo.	No significant difference in ongoing pregnancy overall. Subgroup (age 35–37) showed higher ongoing pregnancy with DKP (41.8% vs. 25.4%).
Huang <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁷	Evaluate anti-adhesion agents post-recanalisation.	400 women were randomised into 4 groups: control, chitosan, <i>Dan-shen</i> , or combination.	Combination chitosan + <i>Dan-shen</i> showed the highest tubal patency and pregnancy rates.
Herbal medicine – Male (1 study)			
Wang <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁸	Evaluate QZD decoction in idiopathic asthenozoospermia.	66 patients randomised: treatment (QZD 150 mL bid) vs. control (levocarnitine 1 g bid).	After 12 weeks, QZD significantly improved progressive and non-progressive sperm motility compared to control. Safe, no adverse effects.

4. Discussion

The studies by Shuai *et al.* ³⁷ and Zhai *et al.* ⁴³ demonstrated that TEAS has beneficial effects, significantly improving IVF outcomes in women with recurrent implantation failure (RIF). These authors also reported enhanced vascular endothelial function, improved endometrial receptivity, and relief of symptoms related to kidney deficiency and blood stasis. Both studies indicate that TEAS is a safe method with a positive impact on ovarian function and endometrial tolerance, potentially contributing to IVF success. Although results regarding pregnancy and live birth rates vary, evidence suggests that TEAS may be particularly valuable for women with RIF.

In women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) undergoing IVF, acupuncture yielded favourable effects during the follicular phase, regulating serum estradiol (E2) and progesterone (P) levels at the time of hCG administration and improving pregnancy rates, as reported by Altutunji *et al.* ⁴¹ and Wu *et al.* ⁴². Both studies highlight the potential of acupuncture as an adjuvant therapy in PCOS, acting through hormonal modulation and optimization of endometrial conditions. Similarly, Yuan *et al.* ⁴⁰, found acupuncture to be a safe and effective adjunct to controlled ovarian stimulation, while Guven *et al.* ³⁹ reported a significant reduction in pre-transfer anxiety among IVF patients.

The use of acupoint stimulation combined with hot compresses of sea salt also appears promising. Xie *et al.* ³⁸ observed that this approach reduced pain and promoted comfort in infertile women undergoing hysterosalpingo-contrast sonography (HyCoSy), suggesting potential benefits for patient experience during diagnostic and therapeutic procedures.

Overall, studies by Shuai, Z. *et al.* (2019), Zhai, Z. J. *et al.* (2022), Altutunji, A. Z. *et al.* (2019), Wu, J. M. *et al.* (2022), and Guven, P. G. *et al.* (2020) indicate that acupuncture contributes not only to improved reproductive outcomes but also to psychological well-

being. Mechanistically, stimulation of specific acupuncture points activates the central nervous system, promoting the release of neurotransmitters such as serotonin and endorphins. This reduces stress and anxiety, regulates the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis, and lowers cortisol production, thereby enhancing emotional balance and supporting IVF success.

Regarding herbal medicine, *DKP*, administered as an oral solution or tablet in combination with oestrogen/progesterone therapy, was shown to improve luteal function in infertile women, although further trials are required to confirm these findings^{44,45}. Chen *et al.*⁴⁶ reported that the *ZYP* improved live birth rates in subgroups of women with a history of miscarriage or advanced maternal age, suggesting particular benefit in these populations. Furthermore, Huang *et al.*⁴⁷, demonstrated that combining chitosan with *Dan-shen* injections effectively maintained tubal patency and improved pregnancy rates compared to either agent alone or controls in women undergoing tubal recanalisation.

Collectively, these studies suggest that herbal medicine may regulate the hypothalamic–pituitary–ovarian axis, balancing oestrogen and progesterone levels. Additional mechanisms include improved uterine and ovarian blood flow (“blood activation”), antioxidant protection of oocytes, and stress regulation through neurotransmitter modulation. Certain herbal formulations may also exert immunomodulatory effects that facilitate embryo implantation^{44–46}

In male infertility, Yu *et al.*³⁶ demonstrated that low-frequency (2 Hz) TEAS significantly improved sperm count, motility, and seminal biochemical markers (NAG, zinc, fructose), effects attributed to the regulation of proteins involved in cell cycle control and sperm function. Similarly, Wang *et al.*⁴⁸ reported that *QZD* enhanced sperm motility, volume, and density in men with idiopathic asthenozoospermia. The promising results described by Yu *et al.*³⁶ and Wang *et al.*⁴⁸ suggest that both acupuncture and herbal decoctions improve sperm quality through mitochondrial enhancement, prevention of cell apoptosis, and reduction of oxidative stress.

5. Final Considerations and Limitations

TCM, through acupuncture and herbal medicine, emerges as a relevant complementary therapeutic approach for infertility, contributing both to the improvement of reproductive parameters (semen quality, ovulatory function, endometrial thickness, implantation, and live birth rates) and to stress reduction, emotional support, and quality of life for couples^{36–41,43–48}.

Promising results are noted, but significant limitations remain: scarcity of RCTs, especially in male infertility, and a predominant focus on intermediate rather than final outcomes. Furthermore, a narrative review does not ensure the quantitative rigour of a meta-analysis.

The most studied herbal formulas include *DKP*, *QZD*, and *Dan-Shen*^{45,46,48}. Acupuncture protocols frequently include points such as GV20, PC6, ST29, RN4, RN3, SP6, and EX-CA1, adjusted to each case^{31,42,43}.

Acupuncture and Chinese herbal medicine appear safe and potentially effective in infertility treatment. However, rigorous studies with standardised protocols and long-term follow-up are needed to consolidate evidence and integrate these therapies more consistently into clinical practice^{6,18,37,42,45,46}.

Regarding limitations of the present study, the review was restricted to a single database (PubMed) and to publications from 2019 to 2025, which may have led to the omission of relevant studies published in other databases or earlier years. In addition, articles in Mandarin were excluded, even though a large proportion of high-quality clinical research on acupuncture and herbal medicine for infertility is published in Chinese, which may have introduced language bias. As this is a narrative review, no formal risk of bias assessment or quantitative synthesis was performed, limiting the ability to draw firm conclusions on efficacy. Finally, the heterogeneity of study designs, populations, and outcome measures further constrains the generalizability of findings.

6. Conclusions

TCM, through acupuncture and herbal medicine, presents itself as a highly relevant complementary therapeutic approach for female and male infertility. Beyond improving clinical parameters such as semen quality, endometrial thickness, and implantation rates, it also contributes to stress reduction, emotional balance, and quality of life—factors often neglected in conventional treatments.

The integration of these practices with conventional medical protocols offers a holistic and synergistic approach, capable of enhancing outcomes and reducing adverse effects. Nonetheless, challenges remain, such as a lack of standardised protocols, scarcity of robust studies (especially in male infertility), and the need for greater methodological rigour.

Future studies with representative samples, clear protocols, and relevant outcomes—such as live birth rates and long-term safety—are fundamental to consolidating the role of TCM in reproductive medicine.

Thus, these therapies represent a valuable and complementary contribution, offering new perspectives of success and hope for couples facing infertility.

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